

Preventing Technology-Enabled Economic Abuse: Insights by Small Business Owners

You are invited to participate in a research study. This form has information to help you decide whether or not you wish to participate - please review it carefully. Your participation is voluntary. Please ask any questions you have about the study or about this form before deciding to participate.

What the study is about

The purpose of this research is to further the understanding of the role technology plays in how small and micro-business owners run by members of groups at heightened risk of harm are attacked online. Our research focuses on three at-risk groups: survivors of intimate partner violence (IPV, for short), Black and ethnic minorities in the United States, and activists or advocates of specific causes. Our research intends to scope the different forms of harm businesses like yours might face, how technology exacerbates these harms, and what kinds of mitigation steps can be taken to limit the impact of attacks.

With more insight into this area, we will advocate for e-commerce websites and other commercial software that you might use to cater to your needs.

What we will ask you to do

If you agree to participate, you will be asked to participate in either a remote or in-person interviews individually (just you and a few research team members) about technology within your business, economic abuse, and helpful mitigations for harm. We expect interviews to last 45-60 minutes although you are free to stop the interview at any point and leave.

We will ask about how you use technology within your business; what kinds of technological attacks you may encounter/encounter while running your business; and what (if any) strategies were helpful in recovering from such attacks.

None of the questions asked will require you to disclose any sensitive information about yourself or detailed, identifiable details of your business. If there is a question you do not want to answer, you may ask to skip the question and you do not have to provide a response. We will take notes on the answers to these questions. All of our notes will be de-identified to protect your privacy. Recording

Risks and discomforts

We anticipate that there could be some risks to you and your business by participating in this research. This study involves the following risks or discomforts:

- **De-identification:** There is a risk that you and your business could be re-identified as participating in this study. We will use data minimization strategies by not asking you for unnecessary and highly personal identifiable information to mitigate this risk. We host each interview in a private video-conferencing room where only individuals invited to or facilitating the group have access to. We will never view your data outside of the premises of the lead researcher's home office or their workplace at Cornell Tech, NYC to reduce the risk of shoulder surfing and confidentiality violations. When reporting information related to you or your business in our research deliverables (e.g., a paper), we will obfuscate some low-level details so that readers should not be able to easily infer your identity.
- **Psychological/emotional distress or discomfort:** There is a possibility that you could recount some experiences of financial abuse that you could find distressing. However, the risk to you is no greater than recounting this information to a trusted friend or therapist. We will also ensure that you will be provided with helpful information for specialist services if you would like to discuss this further.

Please tell the researchers if you believe you are harmed from your participation in the study.

Benefits

We believe that there will be direct benefit to you for participating in this study. By participating in this study we will hopefully contribute to your knowledge about understanding economic abuse for small and medium businesses, how adversaries may be using strategies for harm, and, if appropriate, what protective measures you might be able to put in place. To ensure these benefits, we will leave time to answer any questions you might have about technology.

Audio/Video Recording

We plan to audio record the interview for our notes only. We will delete the audio recordings as soon as we have transcribed them. We will not share the recording with anyone outside the transcription service and the research team. Please indicate below if you are willing to have this interview audio recorded. You may still participate in this study if you are not willing to have the interview recorded. Please let us know by selecting one of the following choices:

- I do not want to have this interview recorded.
- I am willing to have this interview recorded:

Privacy/Confidentiality/Data Security

In this study, you may be asked to provide information that could be used to identify you personally. This information will be kept confidential. Only researchers and others that will keep the information confidential (e.g., regulatory agencies or oversight groups) may access information that could personally identify you.

We will anonymize all data generated from this interview. We will store data in encrypted form at Cornell University with physical and digital access control. The datasets will not be made public and will only be accessible to researchers affiliated with the study. We will publicly reveal information derived from the study, but not anything that would allow you to be identified as having taken part in the study.

Future Use of Data

Information about you collected for this study may be shared with other researchers, used for other research studies, or placed in a data repository. These studies may be similar to this study or completely different. All information that could identify you will be removed before sharing the data or using it for other research studies. We will not ask you for additional permission before sharing the information.

Taking part is voluntary

This research study is voluntary. A participant may refuse to participate before the study begins, quit at any time, skip any questions they are uncomfortable answering, or may ask for previous answers to be deleted. There will be no penalty to a participant for dropping out at any time. You can leave whenever you want.

Access to Your Study Information

We will give you access to the information that is collected about you in this study. We will give you a copy of this form to keep for your records if you would like one. You can also choose to not take or keep a copy of this form.

Contact Information

You are encouraged to ask questions at any time during this study. For information about the study, contact Professor Rosanna Bellini at +1-(646)-997-3600, or at rfb242@cornell.edu.

Please note that we cannot ensure the confidentiality of email communication. If you have any questions or concerns regarding your rights as a subject in this study, you may contact the Institutional Review Board (IRB) for Human Participants at 607-255-6182 or access their website at <http://www.irb.cornell.edu>.

You may also report your concerns or complaints anonymously through Ethicspoint online at www.hotline.cornell.edu or by calling toll free at 1-866-293-3077. Ethicspoint is an independent organization that serves as a liaison between the University and the person bringing the complaint so that anonymity can be ensured.

We will give you a copy of this form to keep for your records if you would like one. You can also choose to not take or keep a copy of this form.

Statement of Consent

By checking below, you are agreeing to participate in this study. Make sure you understand what the study involves before you agree. If you have questions about the study after you agree to participate, you can contact the research team using the information provided above. You may [print/keep] a copy of this form.

[] *I agree to participate in this study*

(Signature of participant)

(Signature of lead researcher)

(Date)